

	TY	A1	Y1	VL	IS	JF	DO	M1	SP	EP	LA
T1	The emergence of specialized newsletters during covid-19: Curated and up-to-date information in an email										
	JOUR	Silva-Rodríguez, A.	2021	30	4	Profesional de la Informacion	10.3145/EPI.2021.JUL.10	Journal Article			
ID	RefID:35-silva-rodríguez2021emergence										
N1	Export Date: 24 November 2025; Cited By: 11										
U7	e300410										
UR	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85112661913&doi=10.3145%2fEPI.2021.JUL.10&partnerID=40&md5=b14cbf89ac148ccbae927ca9ab29639f										
T1	Some viable models for digital public-interest journalism										
	JOUR	Medina-Laverón, M. Breiner, J. Sánchez-Tabernero, A.	2021	30	1	Profesional de la Informacion	10.3145/epi.2021.ene.18	Journal Article			
ID	RefID:34-medina-laverón2021viable										
N1	Export Date: 24 November 2025; Cited By: 17										
U7	e300118										
UR	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85116449933&doi=10.3145%2fepi.2021.ene.18&partnerID=40&md5=7511315e1f2151a6bafdc5963a82036d										
T1	The emergence, innovation, and consolidation of new models for digital journalism: case studies of El Confidencial, elDiario.es and infoLibre										
	JOUR	Peña-Ascacibar, G. Álvarez-Peralta, M.	2021	27	2	Estudios Sobre el Mensaje Periodistico	10.5209/ESMP.71245	Journal Article	593	606	
ID	RefID:33-peña-ascacibar2021emergence										
N1	Export Date: 24 November 2025; Cited By: 4										

UR <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85106480920&doi=10.5209%2fESMP.71245&partnerID=40&md5=c0cf3fae6cab3a43cd978d292ca9b4d4>

T1 **The news media through the lens of the Spanish audience: A matter of trust**

JOUR	Vazquez-Herrero, J. Negreira-Rey, M. Silva-Rodriguez, A. Rodriguez-Vazquez, A.	2022	28	2	Estudios Sobre el Mensaje Periodistico	10.5209/ESMP.77807	Journal Article	447	459
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ID RefID:32-vazquez-herrero2022news

N1 Export Date: 24 November 2025; Cited By: 6

UR <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85131885802&doi=10.5209%2fESMP.77807&partnerID=40&md5=3e7c463435007c4d0573b5e9c1f08cf7>

T1 **Social Implications of Paywalls in a Polarized Society: Representations, Inequalities, and Effects of Citizens' Political Knowledge**

CHAP	Tóth, T. Goyanes, M. Demeter, M. Campos-Freire, F.	2022	97			10.1007/978-3-030-88028-6_13	Book, Section	169	179
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ID RefID:31-tóth2022social

N1 Export Date: 24 November 2025; Cited By: 2

T2 Studies in Big Data

UR https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85130090180&doi=10.1007%2f978-3-030-88028-6_13&partnerID=40&md5=afd6d29be69fa8c3943df94fee68c0a6

T1 **From the Immediacy of the Cybermedia to the Need for Slow Journalism: Experiences from Ibero-America**

	JOUR	Romero-Rodríguez, L. M. Tejedor, S. Castillo-Abdul, B.	2022	16	8	Journalism Practice	10.1080/17512786.2020.1870530	Journal Article	1578	1596	
ID	RefID:30-romero-rodríguez2022immediacy										
N1	Export Date: 23 November 2025; Cited By: 25										
UR	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85099356868&doi=10.1080%2f17512786.2020.1870530&partnerID=40&md5=f53c80a912fe49cac08767f1c324b088										
T1	The Impact of Market-Driven Revenues on the Boundaries of Journalism										
	CHAP	Vara-Miguel, A. Sánchez-Blanco, C.	2023	140			10.1007/978-3-031-43926-1_5	Book, Section	55	70	
ID	RefID:29-vara-miguel2023impact										
N1	Export Date: 23 November 2025; Cited By: 2										
T2	Studies in Big Data										
UR	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85180516574&doi=10.1007%2f978-3-031-43926-1_5&partnerID=40&md5=54eae6fed7f091a9ab2f3e8efb0927d4										
T1	Online music press. The impact of digital subscriptions and paywalls on music news coverage: the case of Rockdelux (2020-2021)										
	JOUR	Alayo Orbeagozo, F.	2023	15	1	Desde el Sur	10.21142/DES-1501-2023-0004	Journal Article			
ID	RefID:28-alayo2023online										
N1	Export Date: 23 November 2025; Cited By: 0										
U7	e0004										
UR	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85197743720&doi=10.21142%2fDES-1501-2023-0004&partnerID=40&md5=33ac0cd6d7600934c39347bc2ddc2843										
T1	E-Commerce as a Source of Revenue in Spanish Digital News Media										

	JOUR	Vara-miguel, A. Sánchez-blanco, C. Negredo-bruna, S. Sádaba-chalezquer, C.	2024	12		Media and Communication	10.17645/mac.7388	Journal Article			
ID	RefID:27-vara-miguel2024ecommerce										
N1	Export Date: 23 November 2025; Cited By: 1										
U7	7388										
UR	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85185122323&doi=10.17645%2fmac.7388&partnerID=40&md5=efb3b56ef8706d0424369efe42ccef9										
T1	Media Consumption and Political Orientation. A Study on the 2023 Spanish Elections										
	JOUR	Jivkova-Semova, D. Rubio-Moraga, Á L. Donofrio, A.	2025	16	1	Maskana	10.18537/mskn.16.01.12	Journal Article	185	202	
ID	RefID:26-jivkova-semova2025media										
N1	Export Date: 23 November 2025; Cited By: 0										
UR	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-105010003367&doi=10.18537%2fmskn.16.01.12&partnerID=40&md5=192958cae1756c8d6fb98c0aeeb15b4b										
T1	Substack, the New “Home” for Cultural Journalism										
	JOUR	Acosta Meneses, M. Y. Gómez-Escalonilla, G.	2025	6	3	Journalism and Media	10.3390/journalmedia6030128	Journal Article			
ID	RefID:25-acosta2025substack										

N1	Export Date: 23 November 2025; Cited By: 0
U7	128
UR	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-105017277728&doi=10.3390%2fjournalmedia6030128&partnerID=40&md5=fece67651e5d30c12dd55a0853bb02a5

T1	Funding Sustainable Online News: Sources of Revenue in Digital-Native and Traditional Media in Spain									
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JOUR	Vara-Miguel, Alfonso Sanchez-Blanco, Cristina Sadaba Chalezquer, Charo Sadaba Negrodo, Samuel	2021	13	20	Sustainability	10.3390/su132011328	Journal Article	11328		English
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ID	RefID:24-vara-miguel2021funding
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Y2	OCT
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KW	media economics
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KW	digital economy
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KW	revenue streams
-----------	-----------------

KW	digital-native media
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KW	news websites
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KW	digital publishing
-----------	--------------------

KW	news organizations
-----------	--------------------

KW	paywall
-----------	---------

KW	crowdfunding
-----------	--------------

KW	BUSINESS MODEL
-----------	----------------

KW	PAID NEWS
-----------	-----------

KW	JOURNALISM
-----------	------------

KW	LEGACY
-----------	--------

KW	PAY									
KW	PERSPECTIVE									
KW	CONSUMPTION									
KW	MONEY									
KW	MAP									
KW	Science & Technology - Other Topics									
KW	Environmental Sciences & Ecology									
AB	<p>Digital news publishers strive to balance revenue streams in their business models: as standard advertising declines, alternatives for sustaining digital journalism arise in the forms of sponsored content, user donations and payments-one-off purchases, subscriptions or memberships, public or private grants, electronic commerce, events and consulting. An exhaustive study found 2874 active online news publications in Spain, and it observed the adoption of such models in early 2021. Advertising remains the most popular source of income for digital news operations (85.8%) and most sites rely on just one or two revenue streams (74.5%). We compare the cases in our census by their origin (digital-native or non-native), geography (local/regional or national/global) and topic scope (generalist or specialized). We find that traditional, national and specialized online media have a broader and more innovative revenue mix than digital-native, regional or local and general-interest news outlets. The comprehensiveness of this pioneering study sheds light for the first time on the risk that the lack of diversification and innovation in funding sources may imperil the financial sustainability of some online news operations in Spain, mostly those with a smaller scope and no backing from a traditional business, according to the results we present here.</p>									
NI	PT: J; NR: 75; TC: 21; J9: SUSTAINABILITY-BASEL; PG: 17; GA: WT8ZU; UT: WOS:000716148000001									
PB	MDPI									
CY	BASEL; MDPI AG, Grosspeteranlage 5, CH-4052 BASEL, SWITZERLAND									
AD	[Vara-Miguel, Alfonso; Sanchez-Blanco, Cristina; Sadaba Chalezquer, Charo Sadaba] Univ Navarra, Sch Commun, Dept Mkt & Media Management, Pamplona 31009, Navarra, Spain. [Negredo, Samuel] Univ Navarra, Sch Commun, Dept Journalism, Pamplona 31009, Navarra, Spain.; Negredo, S (corresponding author), Univ Navarra, Sch Commun, Dept Journalism, Pamplona 31009, Navarra, Spain.; avara@unav.es; csblanco@unav.es; csadaba@unav.es; negredo@unav.es									
DA	OCT									
T1 Subscription to digital press as a barrier to hate speech										
	JOUR	Paz-Rebollo, Maria-Antonia Caceres-Zapatero, Maria-Dolores Martin-Sanchez, Isabel	2021	30	6	Profesional De La Informacion	10.3145/epi.2021.nov.13	Journal Article	e300613	Spanish

ID	RefID:23-paz-rebollo2021subscription
KW	Digital newspapers
KW	Digital journalism
KW	Moderation
KW	Interactivity
KW	Comments
KW	Hate speech
KW	Uncivility
KW	Paywalls
KW	Anonymity
KW	Public discourse
KW	Software
KW	Democratic debate
KW	Journalists
KW	Audiences
KW	USER-GENERATED CONTENT
KW	NEWSPAPER WEBSITES
KW	SECTIONS
KW	CIVILITY
KW	VOICES
KW	Information Science & Library Science
AB	<p>User discussions on digital media usually include offensive comments. This kind of content has become more frequent and intense because of political polarization and the health and economic crises associated with Covid-19. Little is known about the journalists who moderate these forums, how they approach this task in such difficult circumstances, and their opinion about their role in the democratic public debate. To improve understanding of this phenomenon, we carried out 12 semistructured open interviews with moderators from several types of Spanish digital newspapers: generalist, local, and sports. The aim was to ascertain the strengths and weaknesses of moderation filters against hate speech in readers' comments. The results show that the introduction of paywalls in many Spanish newspapers has reduced the intensity of such hate speech, although it has not completely disappeared. These moderation systems are limited mainly to ruling out insults and swearing. There is consensus among the interviewed journalists that most hate speech comments relate to political news. The most frequent topics are racism, xenophobia, misogyny, and homophobia. Several journalists presented the banning of offending users as a possible solution. However, others see this as a business opportunity and proposed solutions ranging from creating specialized moderators to controlling the activity history or trying to educate those users how to participate in a democratic forum. This research contributes to the ongoing debate about moderation systems among media professionals.</p>
N1	PT: J; NR: 41; TC: 6; J9: PROF INFORM; PG: 13; GA: YW8UN; UT: WOS:000753688300018

PB	EDICIONES PROFESIONALES INFORMACION SL-EPI
CY	BARCELONA; MISTRAL, 36, BARCELONA, ALBOLOTE, SPAIN
JA	Prof.Inf.
SN	1386-6710
AD	[Paz-Rebollo, Maria-Antonia; Caceres-Zapatero, Maria-Dolores; Martin-Sanchez, Isabel] Univ Complutense Madrid, Fac Ciencias Informac, Avda Complutense 3, Madrid 28040, Spain.; Paz-Rebollo, MA (corresponding author), Univ Complutense Madrid, Fac Ciencias Informac, Avda Complutense 3, Madrid 28040, Spain.; mapazreb@ucm.es; caceres@ucm.es; imartin@uan.es
DA	NOV-DEC

T1 Collaborative Management and Organization of Digital Media in Spain. Case Study of El Salto, CTXT and La Marea

JOUR	Rodriguez Pallares, Miriam Perez Serrano, Maria Jose	2022	35	Doxa Comunicacion	10.31921/doxacom.n35a1572	Journal Article	127	147	English
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ID	RefID:22-rodriguez2022collaborative
KW	Organizational structure
KW	media management
KW	innovation
KW	revenue model
KW	business models
KW	journalism
KW	NEWS
KW	MODEL
KW	PLATFORMS
KW	Communication

AB The communication sector and, especially, the media sector suffered severely from the consequences of the economic crisis that began in 2008, and is witnessing, once again, the complicated situation derived from the Covid-19 pandemic. Bad strategic decisions; the decrease in advertising investment; the excessive dependence on the financial sector, or the culture of total free of charge typical of the national idiosyncrasy are some of the causes of the emergency situation that drags written journalism in Spain. Through in-depth interviews, innovative actions related to the organization, financing and the product in the journalist sector of digital media in Spain are analysed. Specifically, the cases of El Salto, CTXT and La Marea are analysed. The results are presented divided into six study variables: historical perspective; financing and participation; income diversification; organizational structure; brand equity, and competition. Although the

analyzed examples differ in aspects such as legal personality, all of them coincide in appealing to a traditional, reflective, and with procedural guarantees, they bet on horizontal organizational structures and base their income model on the subscription. The main conclusions show the emergence of initiatives that, faithful to traditional journalistic values, seek to differentiate themselves through strategies and brands whose economic, financial and readership shares are inextricably linked to the concept of niche.

NI PT: J; NR: 62; TC: 2; J9: DOXA COMUN; PG: 21; GA: 3C8MF; UT: WOS:000828871100008

PB UNIV SAN PABLO, FAC HUMANIDADES & CIENCIAS COMUNICACION

CY BOADILLA DEL MONTE; PASEO DE JUAN XXIII 6, BOADILLA DEL MONTE, 28040, SPAIN

JA Doxa Comun.

SN 1696-019X

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DA JUL-DEC

T1 Revenue diversification strategies of online news organisations: subscriptions and memberships

JOUR	Vara-Miguel, Alfonso Sadaba, Charo Negredo, Samuel Sanchez-Blanco, Cristina	2023	32	2	Profesional De La Informacion	10.3145/epi.2023.mar.05	Journal Article			English
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ID RefID:21-vara-miguel2023revenue

KW Digital media

KW Digital journalism

KW News organisations

KW Business models

KW Revenue

KW Revenue strategies

KW Subscriptions

KW Memberships

KW	Digital-native media
KW	Traditional media
KW	Local news media
KW	National news media
KW	Specialised news media
KW	Generalist news media
KW	WILLINGNESS-TO-PAY
KW	BUSINESS MODEL
KW	NATIVE MEDIA
KW	PAID NEWS
KW	PAYWALL
KW	NEWSPAPERS
KW	INNOVATION
KW	LESSONS
KW	LEGACY
KW	Information Science & Library Science
AB	<p>The funding model crisis for newspapers is a matter of public concern; and it is not only a business issue, but also a social and political one, as news organisations are considered to have an irreplaceable function in democratic systems. Technological and social changes have transformed the business model of news organisations so that, in a digital scenario with a strong competition for consumers' attention, they have had to diversify their portfolio of income streams. In such a context, this study analyses the state of the diversification of revenue streams in the Spanish digital media market, using the available data from the total universe of digital media in the country. The article focusses on the two most common revenue streams related to user payment -subscriptions and memberships- and analyses the importance of four variables in this diversification of revenue strategies: their nature (digital native versus traditional), thematic scope (general versus specialised), territorial scope (local versus national), and the type of organisation that promotes it (traditional, new, or independent groups).</p> <p>The data obtained suggest that there are no universal formulae in the implementation of payment models for Spanish digital media. Specifically, there are significant differences in the revenue models between native and non-native digital media. Thus, payment strategies are more prevalent among non-native digital media than among native media. Furthermore, the non-native media that have opted for paid models tend to diversify their sources of income more than the non-native ones based on free model. Additionally, data show that paywalls and memberships are more usual among specialised non-native digital media and generalist native outlets. Also, payments are more often required by local and regional media than national outlets. From the ownership point of view, although the main Spanish media corporations are developing their revenue models, the pay-per-content model is also quite extended among organisations, associations, and foundations not linked with the traditional publishing groups. This study, due to its exhaustiveness, dimensions, and novelty, identifies in detail the current state of the implementation of the pay model for digital media in Spain, which can help and facilitate media managers in their decision-making.</p>
N1	PT: J; NR: 75; TC: 8; J9: PROF INFORM; PG: 14; GA: O1BJ0; UT: WOS:001041238800008
PB	EDICIONES PROFESIONALES INFORMACION SL-EPI
CY	BARCELONA; MISTRAL, 36, BARCELONA, ALBOLOTE, SPAIN

JA	Prof.Inf.									
SN	1386-6710									
AD	[Vara-Miguel, Alfonso; Sadaba, Charo; Negredo, Samuel; Sanchez-Blanco, Cristina] Univ Navarra, Facultad Comunicac, Campus Univ, Pamplona 31009, Spain.; Vara-Miguel, A (corresponding author), Univ Navarra, Facultad Comunicac, Campus Univ, Pamplona 31009, Spain.; avara@unav.edu; csadaba@unav.es; negredo@unav.es; csblanco@unav.es									
T1	The evolution of the media discourse on the implementation of media companies' new digital business models									
	JOUR	Monsalve-Alama, Antonio Ortigosa-Blanch, Arturo Sanchez-Garcia, Javier	2023	190		Technological Forecasting and Social Change	10.1016/j.techfore.2023.122415	Journal Article	122415	English
ID	RefID:20-monsalve-alama2023evolution									
Y2	MAY									
KW	Digital business models									
KW	Media									
KW	Semantic analysis									
KW	PAID CONTENT									
KW	ONLINE NEWS									
KW	NEWSPAPERS									
KW	REVENUE									
KW	LESSONS									
KW	PAYWALL									
KW	Business & Economics									
KW	Public Administration									
AB	This paper examines the discourse of Spanish media outlets to justify changing their digital business model by introducing paywalls. For the last few years, this sector has been introducing new payment models to supplement its income from traditional digital advertising and other revenue models. This article analyzes the evolution of the informational and commercial discourse used by the media to overcome barriers to the implementation of new business models. The sample was defined as a linguistic corpus comprising all content related to the Spanish term for "paywall" from January 2008 to December 2021. Using software designed for this purpose, word association and co-occurrence analyses were carried out. A non-supervised clustering process was also used as the basis for									

	thematic analysis.										
N1	PT: J; NR: 57; TC: 5; J9: TECHNOL FORECAST SOC; EA: FEB 2023; PG: 11; GA: D0AC5; UT: WOS:000965431100001										
PB	ELSEVIER SCIENCE INC										
CY	NEW YORK; STE 800, 230 PARK AVE, NEW YORK, NY 10169 USA										
JA	Technol.Forecast.Soc.Chang.										
SN	0040-1625										
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DA	MAY										
T1	Influence of news interest, payment of digital news, and primary news sources in media trust. A moderated mediation model										
	JOUR	Vara-Miguel, Alfonso Medina, Mercedes Gutierrez-Renteria, Maria Elena	2024	21	4	Journal of Media Business Studies	10.1080/16522354.2023.2214447	Journal Article	315	339	English
ID	RefID:19-vara-miguel2024influence										
Y2	OCT 1										
KW	Media trust										
KW	paywall										
KW	media exposure										
KW	media sources										
KW	news interest										
KW	SELECTIVE EXPOSURE										
KW	PEOPLE WATCH										
KW	FAKE NEWS										
KW	CREDIBILITY										

KW	CONSUMPTION										
KW	JOURNALISM										
KW	COMMUNICATION										
KW	ASSOCIATION										
KW	SKEPTICISM										
KW	PREDICTORS										
KW	Business & Economics										
AB	This study investigated the mediating effect of the primary type of news source used by audiences on the relationship between interest in news and media trust. In addition, this study explored the moderating role of payments for digital news. Based on 12,252 respondents from six countries (the United Kingdom, the United States, France, Spain, Germany, and Finland), the study confirms that the type of news source chosen by audiences significantly mediates the relationship between interest and media trust. This mediation is not moderated by the payments for digital news. Furthermore, there is no direct association between payment and media trust, although data shows that direct effect of interest in media trust is slightly moderated by payment for digital news.										
NI	PT: J; NR: 90; TC: 3; J9: J MEDIA BUS STUD; EA: MAY 2023; PG: 25; GA: K5E4W; UT: WOS:000990892300001										
PB	ROUTLEDGE JOURNALS, TAYLOR & FRANCIS LTD										
CY	ABINGDON; 2-4 PARK SQUARE, MILTON PARK, ABINGDON OX14 4RN, OXON, ENGLAND										
JA	J.Media Bus.Stud.										
SN	1652-2354										
AD	[Vara-Miguel, Alfonso; Medina, Mercedes] Univ Navarra, Dept Mkt & Media Management, Pamplona, Spain. [Gutierrez-Renteria, Maria Elena] Univ Panamericana, Sch Commun, Guadalajara, Mexico.; Vara-Miguel, A (corresponding author), Univ Navarra, Dept Mkt & Media Management, Pamplona, Spain.; avara@unav.es										
DA	OCT 1										
T1	Sports Journalists and Readers: Journalism and User Incivility										
	JOUR	Bonaut, Joseba Vicent-Ibanez, Mireya Paz-Rebollo, Maria Antonia	2024	18	2	Journalism Practice	10.1080/17512786.2023.2222730	Journal Article	356	373	English
ID	RefID:18-bonaut2024sports										
Y2	FEB 7										

KW	Digital sports newspapers
KW	As
KW	Marca
KW	readers' comments
KW	anti-social behavior
KW	Spain
KW	COVID 19
KW	subscription
KW	ONLINE
KW	WOMEN
KW	COMMUNICATION
KW	DETERMINANTS
KW	MODERATION
KW	PATTERNS
KW	CIVILITY
KW	MEDIA
AB	<p>This article assesses the impact of sports journalism style on uncivil conversations, by analyzing the news that has generated the most deleted comments and the published readers' comments. The two sports newspapers with the largest number of readers in Spain (As and Marca) between 2019 and 2020 are compared. The analyzed journalistic pieces in both newspapers are proven to promote controversy and user participation, thus creating a polarized and strongly confronted community. Journalists lose their status as professionals by using a subjective, emotional and colloquial style, and they become mere commentators who can be discredited. This style is the breeding ground for uncivil conversations. Localized hate expressions are ideological: Spanish nationalism confronts Catalan independence in such a way that the world of football becomes dependent on the country's politics. There is no lack of negative gender stereotypes either in the predominantly male order of sport. Since no changes were observed during the pandemic, it can be established that these characteristics are part of the journalistic routine. Only the paywall introduced by As in the second half of 2020 change conversations: the number of messages, including deleted ones, was reduced, and positive feelings advanced in more rational conversations.</p>
NI	PT: J; NR: 52; TC: 4; J9: JOURNAL PRACT; SI: SI; EA: JUN 2023; PG: 18; GA: DZ9E1; UT: WOS:001003520200001
PB	ROUTLEDGE JOURNALS, TAYLOR & FRANCIS LTD
CY	ABINGDON; 2-4 PARK SQUARE, MILTON PARK, ABINGDON OX14 4RN, OXON, ENGLAND
JA	Journal.Pract.
SN	1751-2786

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DA	FEB 7										
T1	Rethinking the use of data: Media's attempts to move away from clickbait and towards audience engagement										
	JOUR	Laferrara, Valentina Justel-Vazquez, Santiago Javier Mico-Sanz, Josep Lluís	2023		26	Adcomunica-Revista Científica De Estrategias E Tendencias E Innovacion En Comunicacion	10.6035/adcomunica.7187	Journal Article	153	174	English
ID	RefID:17-laferrara2023rethinking										
Y2	JUL										
KW	Journalism										
KW	Business Model										
KW	Analytics										
KW	Social Media										
KW	Clickbait										
KW	Engagement										
KW	WEB ANALYTICS										
KW	JOURNALISTIC FIELD										
KW	NEWS										
KW	METRICS										
KW	CRISIS										
KW	FUTURE										
KW	SENSE										
KW	RISK										
KW	Communication										

AB This article studies the use of web analytics and social media in newsrooms that are committed to business models based on audience loyalty and pay-for-content. It is based on 28 in-depth interviews with news workers from 11 media outlets in five European countries: Spain, France, Italy, Germany, and the UK. It reveals that the media are committed to prioritising quality indicators (page views, comments, etc.) over quantity indicators (page views, unique users, etc.), although they still cannot ignore the latter due to their historical dependence on advertising as a source of revenue. Social networks play an essential role in their audience loyalty strategies, but the lack of transparency of these platforms arouses misgivings in some newsrooms. The commitment to loyalty-based business models does not mean abandoning work with audience data, but rather significantly changing the way they are approached. The determined commitment to guaranteeing the success of the business model has significantly changed the work with audience data and social networks, leading the media to abandon clickbait content and prioritise quality content.

NI PT: J; NR: 66; TC: 0; J9: ADCOMUNICA; PG: 22; GA: O9AL9; UT: WOS:001046672400008

PB ASOC DESARROLLO COMUNICACION

CY CASTELLON; DESPACHO RR 0022 SD, EDIF RECTORADO CAMPUS RIU SEC, CASTELLON, 12006, SPAIN

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DA JUL

T1 **AI Implementation Strategies in the Spanish Press Media: Organizational Dynamics, Application Flows, Uses and Future Trends**

JOUR	Ceide, Cesar Fieiras Vaz- Alvarez, Martin Gonzalez, Isaac Maroto	2024	55	Tripodos	10.51698/tripodos.2024.55.01	Journal Article	10	32	English
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ID RefID:16-ceide2024ai

KW journalism

KW automation

KW artificial intelligence

KW ChatGPT

KW news

KW ARTIFICIAL-INTELLIGENCE

KW	IMPACT									
KW	Communication									
AB	This research analyses the artificial intelligence application strategies adopted by the Spanish press media at the height of the generative AI boom, extending previous studies on integrating AI technology into journalistic routines. We studied the dynamics of implementation of AI solutions in the main newspapers in Spain, determining the departments or professionals involved, the current uses, and how AI affects their organization chart and professional profiles, as well as providing insights into the future trends of this technology in the sector. For this purpose, a qualitative methodology was employed, based on interviews with a purposive sample of executives from the 10 newspapers with the largest circulation in Spain: El Pais, , La Vanguardia, , Marca, , La Voz de Galicia, , As, , ABC, , El Mundo, , El Correo, , El Diario Vasco and Mundo Deportivo. . The results reveal that AI is conceived in the Spanish press media as an assistant aimed at optimizing all kinds of mechanical processes and existing products, not at amplifying coverage or generating final pieces that reduce the standard of quality essential to their subscription model. Groups such as Prisa, Vocento or Unidad Editorial centralize their AI strategy, while Grupo God & oacute; delegates this management to its headers. These newspapers consider that AI will boost the renewal of job profiles in their structures, despite the fact that they do not currently have strictly specialized professionals.									
N1	PT: J; NR: 37; TC: 10; J9: TRIPODOS; PG: 23; GA: J1Y5T; UT: WOS:001335097200001									
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T1	Following Professional Journalists on Social Media and Paying Intent for Online News: A Moderated Mediation Model in Spain and Germany									
	JOUR	Goyanes, Manuel Halo, Gergo	2025			Journalism Practice	10.1080/17512786.2025.2507088	Journal Article		English
ID	RefID:15-goyanes2025professional									
KW	Social media									
KW	paying intent									
KW	digital journalism									
KW	online news									
KW	culture of free									
KW	paywall									
KW	WILLINGNESS-TO-PAY									
KW	CONSUMPTION									

KW	Communication
AB	Amidst the challenges faced by news organizations due to a culture of free access and the transition to digital subscription models, this study examines how following professional journalism on social media relates to the intent to pay for online news. We propose a moderated mediation model, where following professional journalism on social media influences paying intent through interest in paywalled content, moderated by exposure to paywalled information. Using survey data from Spain (N = 2337) and Germany (N = 2213), our findings reveal a positive and statistically significant association between (1) following professional journalism on social media and interest in paywalled content, (2) interest in paywalled content and paying intent, and (3) following professional journalism on social media and paying intent. Furthermore, in Germany, the moderated mediation analysis shows that higher exposure to paywalled content strengthens the indirect effect, reinforcing the link between following journalists, interest in paywalled content, and paying intent. These findings contribute to research on the economics of online news, highlighting the role of social media in fostering readers interest in paid content and its implications for the financial sustainability of news organizations.
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